

Data-driven flood hazard zonation of Italy

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ABSTRACT

We present Flood-SHE, a data-driven, statistically-based procedure for the delineation of areas expected to be inundated by river floods. We applied Flood-SHE in the 23 River Basin Authorities (RBAs) in Italy using information on the presence or absence of inundations obtained from existing flood zonings as the dependent variable, and six hydro-morphometric variables computed from a 10 m × 10 m DEM as covariates. We trained 96 models for each RBA using 32 combinations of the hydro-morphometric covariates for the three return periods, for a total of 2208 models, which we validated using 32 model sets for each of the covariate combinations and return periods, for a total of 3072 validation models. In all the RBAs, Flood-SHE delineated accurately potentially inundated areas that matched closely the corresponding flood zonings defined by physically-based hydro-dynamic flood routing and inundation models. Flood-SHE delineated larger to much larger areas as potentially subject of being inundated than the physically-based models, depending on the quality of the flood information. Analysis of the sites with flood human consequences revealed that the new data-driven inundation zones are good predictors of flood risk to the population of Italy. Our experiment confirmed that a small number of hydro-morphometric terrain variables is sufficient to delineate accurate inundation zonings in a variety of physiographical settings, opening to the possibility of using Flood-SHE in other areas. We expect the new data-driven inundation zonings to be useful where flood zonings built on hydrological modelling are not available, and to decide where improved flood hazard zoning is needed.

1. Introduction

From 1980 to 2016, at least 225,000 people were killed or went missing due to river and coastal floods, with damage exceeding US\$ 1.6 trillion (Jongman et al., 2018). Floods affect annually 21-million people globally and the number is expected to reach 54-million by 2030. Given these figures, it is not surprising that societies have long attempted to mitigate flood risk adopting structural and non-structural measures (Kundzewicz, 2002). The later include land management based on flood hazard and risk zoning (Dawson et al., 2011) designed exploiting 1-D or 2-D hydro-dynamic flood routing and inundation models (Grimaldi et al., 2013; Manfreda et al., 2015; Rahmati et al., 2016b; Teng et al., 2017; Bermúdez et al., 2019; Galuppini et al., 2020).

A known drawback of hydro-dynamic flood routing and inundation models is the amount and quality of the information needed to run the models, and the computational demand, which confines their

application to areas of limited extent (Sampson et al., 2012; Bermúdez et al., 2019) and for which accurate topographic information is available (Xia et al., 2019; Ming et al., 2020); although examples exist at the continental (Alferi et al., 2014, 2015) and the global (Sampson et al., 2015; Dottori et al., 2016) scales. Despite unquestioned progresses in model accuracy and computational efficiency, hydro-dynamic flood routing and inundation models remain poorly suited to model very large areas at high resolution (Teng et al., 2017).

The alternative are data-driven models that attempt to identify areas that can be inundated based on functional relationships between morphometric and hydrological variables, and the known or inferred presence or absence of inundations (Das, 2019; Wang et al., 2019a). Here, we present the Flood – Statistical Hazard Evaluation (Flood-SHE) procedure for the data-driven delineation of “potentially inundated areas” (PIAs) exploiting information on “flood prone areas” (FPAs) identified through physically-based modelling and an innovative

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optimal selection of areas that cannot be inundated i.e., the “marginal areas” (Degiorgis et al., 2012; Manfreda et al., 2014, 2015, 2015; Gnecco et al., 2017). The aim of Flood-SHE is to facilitate the delineation on PIAs where hydro-dynamic flood routing and inundation modelling are difficult, or costly to prepare.

2. Previous works

In the literature, no standard data-driven approach exists to delineate areas that can be inundated by river floods, or to estimate the depth of the water in the PIAs (Das, 2019; Wang et al., 2019a). Authors have tested expert-based, multi-criteria decision analysis methods, including Analytic Hierarchy Process (Papaioannou et al., 2015; Khosravi et al., 2016; Rahmati et al., 2016b; Das, 2019; Vojtek and Vojteková, 2019), Analytic Network Process (Dano et al., 2019; Kanani-Sadat et al., 2019), and the VIKOR and TOPSIS multiple criteria decision-making methods (Arabameri et al., 2019; Khosravi et al., 2019), chiefly where inundation data were scant (Hall et al., 2005; Elshorbagy et al., 2017; Santos et al., 2019). Other authors have trialled bivariate statistical classification methods, including frequency ratio (Good, 1950; Tehrany et al., 2015a, 2017; Rahmati et al., 2016a; Liuzzo et al., 2019; Sahana and Patel, 2019) and multivariate classification techniques (Khosravi et al., 2016; Tehrany et al., 2017, 2019b; Choubin et al., 2019; Costache, 2019; Davoudi Moghaddam et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019; Tien Bui et al., 2019). Still other authors have tested machine-learning algorithms (Degiorgis et al., 2012; Tehrany et al., 2015a,b, 2019a; Wang et al., 2015, 2019b; Chapi et al., 2017; Kourgialas and Karatzas, 2017; Shafizadeh-Moghadam et al., 2018; Ahmadlou et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2019; Darabi et al., 2019; Manfreda and Samela, 2019).

The data-driven studies cover areas of very different extent, from two (Bermúdez et al., 2019) to 795,000 km² (Try et al., 2019), and most of them adopt the grid cell as the mapping unit of reference, with a wide range of resolutions, from 1 m × 1 m (Bermúdez et al., 2019) to ≈ 10 km × 10 km (Zhao et al., 2018). Several authors (Degiorgis et al., 2012; Manfreda et al., 2014, 2015, 2015; Gnecco et al., 2017) used the HydroSHEDS DEM (Lehner et al., 2008) with resolutions in the range from 3 arc-second (≈90 m at the equator) to 5 min (~10 km at the equator). Most of the studies cover large and very large areas with resolutions dependent on the available DEM e.g., 20 m × 20 m for Greece (Kourgialas and Karatzas, 2017) and Canada (Elshorbagy et al., 2017), 50 m × 50 m for Slovakia (Vojtek and Vojteková, 2019), 90 m × 90 m for Portugal and the USA (Samela et al., 2017; Santos et al., 2019), up to about 10 km × 10 km for China (Zhao et al., 2018).

To train the classification models, investigators used point and area inundation data. Point data were taken typically from historical archives (Khosravi et al., 2016; Ahmadlou et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019) or maps showing the locations of inundated sites (Tehrany et al., 2015b, 2019b, 2019b; Try et al., 2019), with the number of inundation points generally limited, from less than 100 to about 200 (Siahkamari et al., 2018; Choubin et al., 2019; Kanani-Sadat et al., 2019). Area data were taken from maps showing the extent of single inundation events (Sahana and Patel, 2019; Tehrany et al., 2019a), or zones identified as flood prone by hydro-dynamic flood routing and inundation models (Degiorgis et al., 2012; Manfreda et al., 2014, 2015; De Risi et al., 2015; Rahmati et al., 2016b; Bermúdez et al., 2019; Manfreda and Samela, 2019). In addition, the classification models need information on points or areas that cannot be inundated i.e., the “marginal areas” (MAs) (Degiorgis et al., 2012; Manfreda et al., 2014, 2015, 2015; Gnecco et al., 2017).

To train the models, authors have used two types of conditioning factors i.e., variables describing (i) morphometric and hydrological properties derived from a DEM (Degiorgis et al., 2012; Manfreda et al., 2014; De Risi et al., 2015; Elshorbagy et al., 2017; Gnecco et al., 2017; Samela et al., 2017), and (ii) environmental conditions e.g., land cover (Shafizadeh-Moghadam et al., 2018; Arabameri et al., 2019; Darabi et al., 2019; Sahana and Patel, 2019; Wang et al., 2019a), land use (Wang et al., 2015; Chapi et al., 2017; Kourgialas and Karatzas, 2017;

Shafizadeh-Moghadam et al., 2018; Ahmadlou et al., 2019; Choubin et al., 2019; Khosravi et al., 2019; Liuzzo et al., 2019), lithology (Shafizadeh-Moghadam et al., 2018; Ahmadlou et al., 2019), and distance from rivers (Davoudi Moghaddam et al., 2019; Mind'je et al., 2019). For the later, an important difference exists; some authors measured the distance as the planimetric distance to the nearest stream along the flow direction (Degiorgis et al., 2012; Manfreda et al., 2014, 2015, 2015; Papaioannou et al., 2015; Elshorbagy et al., 2017; Gnecco et al., 2017), whereas other authors measured the Euclidean, geometric distance from the nearest stream (Wang et al., 2015; Rahmati et al., 2016a; Siahkamari et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2019; Das, 2019; Mind'je et al., 2019; Tien Bui et al., 2019). We stress that the distance along the flow direction is a more meaningful measure than the geometric distance to explain flooding and inundation.

3. The Flood-SHE procedure

Based on hydro-morphometric terrain variables, and information on flooded or potentially flooded areas, the Flood-Statistical Hazard Evaluation (Flood-SHE) procedure exploits a multivariate classification to delineate “potentially inundated areas” (PIAs) i.e., areas that are normally dry but can be covered by water during a river flooding event (Fig. 1).

The first step of the procedure consists of the acquisition of the relevant data, namely a digital representation of the topography of the study area, in the form of a DEM (§ 4.1), and geographical inundation data (§ 4.2). The DEM must cover the entire area with planar and vertical resolutions and accuracies adequate to capture the relevant topographic and hydrographic features that control river flooding in the area. Errors and inconsistencies in the DEM will reflect in the classification model. The geographical inundation data can be obtained from different sources and do not have to cover the entire study area, but they should be representative of the entire study area i.e., they should characterize the main morphometric and hydrologic properties of the area.

The second step consists of two parts, with the scope of preparing the

Fig. 1. Logical framework of the Flood – Statistical Hazard Evaluation (Flood-SHE) procedure for the delineation of “predicted inundation areas” (PIAs) through statistical classification modelling of hydro-morphometric terrain variables and information on flooded or potentially flooded areas.

hydro-morphometric variables and the inundation data for the statistical classification. One part computes the hydrologic and morphologic variables (model “covariates”) from the DEM (§ 4.1). The explanatory variables can show local terrain characteristics e.g., the local height or terrain gradient in a grid cell, or they can show broader terrain characteristics e.g., the hydrologic distance or difference in elevation between a grid cell and the catchment outlet, the flow accumulation area above a grid cell. The second part of the pre-processing step delineates the model classification training and validation areas (§ 4.3, 4.4). The training areas are all the areas for which “inundation information” is

available and, typically, they are (or can be) shown by a binary (0/1) map, where “1” is assigned to the grid cells that fall in an inundated area, and “0” to the grid cells that do not fall in an inundated area, based on the available information.

The third step consists in training the classification model (§ 4.5). For the purpose, Flood-SHE uses logistic regression (Tolles and Meurer, 2016) adopting the presence or absence of known or modelled inundation areas in each grid cell as the dependent variable, and the hydro-morphologic variables computed in second step as the independent covariates. The procedure can use a single combination or multiple

Fig. 2. (A) Location and extent of the 23 River Basin Authorities (RBAs) used in this work, each encompassing a single, or multiple catchments. Numbers in the RBAs refer to the RBA # in Table 1. Grey rectangles with capital letters show location of insets C, D, E, F. (B) Map shows “flood prone areas” (FPAs) defined by the RBAs through hydro-dynamic flood routing and inundation modelling, for three return periods, τ_3 (red) $>$ τ_2 (light blue) $>$ τ_1 (blue) (ISPRA, 2015). (C), (D), (E), and (F) show enlarged parts of map (B). Location of the enlargements shown by grey rectangles in (A). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

combinations of explanatory variables; and a single classification model or multiple models can be trained. Calibration of a single model is more rapid and less demanding computationally, but it does not allow to estimate the model uncertainty. Training of multiple models is more time consuming and demanding computationally, but it allows for the estimation of the epistemic uncertainty associated with the statistical classification.

The fourth step (§ 4.6, 4.7) validates the trained classification model (s). This can be achieved in different ways, depending on the extent and complexity of the study area and of the type, extent, and complexity of the inundation information. Proper validation of the model(s) allows quantifying the performance of the classification model(s). Where multiple combinations of explanatory variables are used to train the model(s), the validation will allow to select the optimal combination(s) of model covariates.

The last step of the procedure prepares the model outputs, including a single predicted inundation map or a set of inundation maps, showing results for a single or for multiple return periods, which are used to prepare water-depth maps (§ 4.8).

4. Application in Italy

We tested Flood-SHE in 23 River Basin Authorities (RBAs) in Italy covering $\sim 301,300 \text{ km}^2$ (Fig. 2).

4.1. Hydro-morphometric variables

To test the procedure, we used the $10 \text{ m} \times 10 \text{ m}$ TinItaly DEM, the most accurate, freely available DEM covering Italy (Tarquini et al., 2007, 2012, 2017, 2012), which is used for regional hydrological, geomorphological, and geological studies (Favalli et al., 2012; Bisson et al., 2014; Domeneghetti et al., 2016). Specifically, we used the DEM to calculate seven hydro-morphometric variables, i.e.

- the planimetric (horizontal) distance L , and the elevation (vertical) difference H , between each grid cell and the nearest stream, measured along the hydrologic flow direction, in meter (Try et al., 2019; Manfreda et al., 2014);
- the planimetric (horizontal) distance D , and the elevation (vertical) difference V , between each grid cell and the basin outlet, measured along the hydrologic flow direction, also in meter (Jasiewicz and Metz, 2011);
- the local terrain slope S , in degree, calculated on a 3×3 -cell kernel (Horn, 1981);
- the order of the stream channel into which each grid cell drains O , using the Shreve (1966) ordering scheme;
- the local terrain roughness G , measured by the mean length of the unit normal vectors to the topographic surface in a 3×3 -cell kernel (Grohmann et al., 2011).

4.2. Inundation data

We obtained inundation data for each RBA from digital hazard maps showing “flood prone areas” (FPAs) identified through hydro-dynamic flood routing and inundation modelling for (i) frequent floods with average return period $30 \leq \tau_3 \leq 50$ years, (ii) less frequent floods with average return period $100 \leq \tau_2 \leq 200$ years, and for (iii) rare floods with return period $\tau_1 > 200$ years.

4.3. River network

The Flood-SHE procedure requires a reference river network. Using the r.watershed module of the GRASS GIS (Jasiewicz and Metz, 2011), and assuming single flow directions to minimize issues related to artificial flow dispersion (Orlandini and Moretti, 2009), for each TinItaly DEM grid cell we computed the corresponding flow accumulation area,

and we considered all the cells with a flow accumulation area larger than a predefined threshold as being part of the river network. To select the threshold, we adopted the Freedman and Diaconis (1981) method to select the size of the “bin” used to calculate the frequency distribution of the flow accumulation areas inside each FPAs. Next, we approximated the empirical frequency distribution with branches of an equilateral hyperbola, and we selected the flow accumulation area corresponding to the maximum curvature along the hyperbola as the threshold T , to initiate the stream network. The obtained values range from 0.02 km^2 (RBA #20) to 0.3 km^2 (#2), with most of the RBAs having $0.04 \leq T \leq 0.06 \text{ km}^2$ (Table 1).

4.4. Modelling domain

In Italy, most of the landscape is hilly or mountainous and it is not affected by river floods. Thus, using the entire extent of an RBA to train and validate the classification models may bias the terrain classification in favour of areas that cannot be inundated. To address the issue, we constrained the modelling domain. We began by identifying all the grid cells that drained into the reference river network in the FPAs. Some of the selected grid cells were inside the FPAs; and we gave them a value of “1”. Other grid cells were outside the FPAs. Following Degiorgis et al. (2012), Gnecco et al. (2017a), and Manfreda et al. (2015, 2014), we considered these cells “marginal areas” (MAs), and we gave them a value of “0”.

We then used a hexagonal tessellation – which minimizes the differences between the tassel centroid and edge – to partition the RBAs, with hexagons about 5.412 km^2 in size, and we selected the subset of hexagons that contained grid cells classified as FPAs (1) or MAs (0) (Table 1). Hexagons that did not contain FPAs or MAs were excluded from the analyses. For each RBA, the subset of grid cells encompassing FPAs or MAs became our training and validation modelling domain. Since the extent of the FPAs was different for the three return periods, we used the domain that corresponded to the shortest return period, τ_3 that is fully encompassed in the domains of the longer return periods. We choose the size of the hexagons through an expert compromise between the necessity to constrain the classification modelling to the portions of the RBA that – in principle – can be inundated, and the need to have a sufficiently large number of cells covering each hexagon and of hexagons in each RBA, to obtain reliable statistical results.

4.5. Model training

For model training, we selected randomly 70% of the hexagons in the modelling domains i.e., hexagons having grid cells classified as FPAs (1) or MAs (0). We trained separately 96 models for each of the 23 RBAs i.e., one model for each of the 32 covariate (L, H, D, V, S, O, G) combinations for each of the three considered return periods (τ_1, τ_2, τ_3). More specifically, we trained the three simplest models – one for each return period – using only the L and H covariates, which – based on their known or inferred relevance (Degiorgis et al., 2012; Gnecco et al., 2017; Manfreda et al., 2015; Try et al., 2019) – we also used to train all the other models, with combinations of one to five of the other covariates (D, V, S, O, G). Overall, in the 23 RBAs we trained 2208 models.

The logistic regression models used to classify the RBA landscape assigned to each grid cell the probability that the cell pertained to the class of “potentially inundated areas” (PIAs) and did not pertain to the “marginal areas” (MAs). To obtain a binary (0/1) map showing PIAs (1) and MAs (0), we selected a cut off value to assign a grid cell with a probability larger than the threshold a value of 1 (PIA), and a grid cell with a probability lower than the threshold a value of 0 (MA). For each classification model, we selected the threshold that maximized jointly the model sensitivity and specificity (Jolliffe and Stephenson, 2003; Fawcett, 2006).

Table 1

Statistics for the 23 River Basin Authorities (RBAs) considered in the work. See Fig. 2 for geographical location of the RBAs. Area, extent of the RBAs in km². *T* is the flow accumulation threshold, in km². HMT is the hydrological model type: N, unknown type; B, 2D modelling; M, 1-D modelling; F, unknown flow regime; U, unsteady flow regime; S, steady flow regime; G, geomorphological approach; H, historic information approach. n.a., information not available. FPA, percentage of the RBA mapped as “flood prone areas” defined through hydro-dynamic flood routing and inundation modelling. PIA are percentages of the RBA classified as “potentially inundated area”. *E*, number of hexagons including FPA or MA cells, in each RBA. TR_{μ} and TR_{σ} are the mean and standard deviation of the True Rate. CV is coefficient of variation. BCC is the best combination of hydro-morphometric model covariates.

RBA #	Area km ²	%	<i>T</i> km ²	FPA %	HMT	PIA %	<i>E</i>	TR_{μ}	TR_{σ}	CV BCC
1	68,733	22.4	116.9	22.73	MB SU GH	43.39	9438	0.57	0.25	0.43 LHGO
2	6281	2.0	16.7	1.1	MB SU	5.32	225	0.77	0.22	0.29 LHSG
3	28,039	9.1	37.9	17.31	MB SU	34.92	1280	0.41	0.18	0.44 LHSG
4	7673	2.5	14.1	0.64	MB SU	10.46	163	0.58	0.24	0.41 LHSG
5	3201	1.0	13.2	2.52	MB SU	13.8	398	0.64	0.21	0.32 LHG
6	18,255	6.0	31.3	21.66	M U GH	29.21	1608	0.63	0.19	0.31 LHS
7	2131	0.7	9.3	9.77	B U	13.67	255	0.57	0.21	0.37 LHS
8	1660	0.5	9.5	18.24	MB F	21.06	286	0.64	0.22	0.34 LHO
9	9235	3.0	40.7	22.63	N U GH	30.24	918	0.56	0.18	0.31 LHGO
10	2803	0.9	11.1	25.89	N F GH	32.92	474	0.63	0.18	0.29 LHSG
11	5825	1.9	19.6	22.65	N F GH	35.7	556	0.55	0.15	0.28 LHGO
12	17,522	5.7	76.8	4.65	M S	18.45	929	0.58	0.21	0.37 LHO
13	3632	1.2	15.8	3.97	B U	33.88	200	0.53	0.21	0.40 LHSGO
14	9830	3.2	13.7	2.13	MB SU G	18.09	324	0.55	0.22	0.40 LHG
15	16,541	5.4	39.9	4.59	MB SU G	27.25	950	0.60	0.22	0.37 LHG
16	4773	1.6	12.0	4.48	M U	32.76	482	0.54	0.18	0.34 LHSGO
17	20,192	6.6	27.2	4.43	N SU	36.71	1378	0.60	0.23	0.39 LHGO
18	4027	1.3	15.0	2.88	n.a.	18.14	192	0.55	0.20	0.37 LHG
19	8980	2.9	22.7	3.27	MB SU	23.67	420	0.59	0.22	0.38 LHG
20	1693	0.6	3.9	2.67	MB SU	20.83	179	0.67	0.22	0.33 LHG
21	15,348	5.0	10.5	3.91	M S	18.36	2035	0.84	0.17	0.20 LHSGO
22	26,021	8.5	14.3	1.78	MB SU	17.48	578	0.60	0.23	0.38 LHS
23	24,287	7.9	20.6	6.06	M S	31.06	1456	0.55	0.18	0.33 LHGOV
Min	1660		3.9	0.64		5.32	163	0.41	0.15	0.20 LHSGO
Max	68,733		116.9	25.89		43.39	9438	0.84	0.25	0.44 LHSG
Mean	13,334		25.8	9.13		24.67	1075	0.60	0.21	0.35
Median	8980		15.8	4.48		23.67	482	0.58	0.21	0.37

4.6. Predicted potentially inundated areas

Exploiting the trained models, and their related thresholds, for each of the 23 RBAs (Fig. 2A), for 32 different combinations of the seven hydro-morphometric covariates (L, H, D, V, S, O, G), and for each of the three considered return periods (τ_1 , τ_2 , τ_3), we prepared separate binary maps showing the presence/absence of the predicted PIAs. We then merged the three original binary maps into a single composite map adopting the following criteria: (i) grid cells in areas with rare (τ_1), less frequent (τ_2), and frequent (τ_3) floods, were assigned values of 1, 2, and 3, respectively; (ii) grid cells for which estimates for multiple return periods were available, were given the value corresponding to the lowest return period ($\tau_3 < \tau_2 < \tau_1$); and (iii) grid cells pertaining to the marginal areas (MAs) in all three original maps were given a value of 0.

4.7. Model validation

To measure the performance of such a large ensemble of classification models, we prepared 32 validation sets, selecting randomly for each set 30% of the hexagons in the modelling domains i.e., hexagons with grid cells classified by the RBAs as FPAs (1) or by us as MAs (0). Of the 32 validation sets, 31 sets included both “within-sample” and “out-of-sample” hexagons, and the last set collected all the hexagons that were not used for model training (“out-of-sample” hexagons). Due to the large computational time required to train the models, we opted for a single training dataset for each variable combination.

We evaluated the performance of the classification models comparing our predicted PIAs to the FPA. We performed the comparison for all the hexagons in the validation sets – 30% of the hexagons in the modelling domains – considering the model performance separately for each hexagon in the validation set using the coefficient of variation, $CV = TR_{\sigma}/TR_{\mu}$, where TR_{μ} is the mean and TR_{σ} is the standard deviation of the True Rate (Fawcett, 2006; Sokolova and Lapalme, 2009) computed

for all the hexagons. TR_{μ} measures the average performance and TR_{σ} the spatial homogeneity of the prediction. Overall, the best models have $0.20 \leq CV \leq 0.44$, with 50% of the models having $CV \leq 0.37$ (Table 1). Given the large number of grid cells used for the model training and validation (the single hexagons included from a few hundreds to 54,000 cells), we maintain that the training and validations sets were adequate for estimating the central tendency of the CV, and the associated uncertainty.

Fig. 3 shows a composite map portraying for each RBA the best PIA model.

4.8. Maximum expected water depth

Based on the obtained PIA composite map (Fig. 3), and using a simple geometrical approach, we calculated the expected depth of the water, *W* (in meters) in the PIAs, for the three considered return periods. We performed the calculation in three steps. First, we assumed that along the PIA perimeter the water depth was null, $W = 0$, and we attributed to each grid cell along the perimeter of a PIA the elevation of the corresponding DEM grid cell. Second, to all the grid cells inside the PIA, we attributed the elevation of the nearest cell along the perimeter. To reduce local errors and inconsistencies, we used a smoothing kernel to adjust the representation of the water surface level in the PIA. Lastly, for each grid cell, we subtracted the elevation of the topographic surface (obtained from the DEM) to the computed water surface level, to obtain a map showing the estimated water depth in the PIA. Where the extent of the PIA was large or very large, the purely geometric procedure resulted in local, unrealistically large inundation water depths. To address the issue, in these local areas we arbitrarily set the maximum water depth to 4 m Fig. 4 shows examples of the modelled water depth for the shortest return period, τ_3 .

Fig. 3. Maps show modelled potentially inundated areas (PIAs) for the three considered return periods, τ_3 (red) $< \tau$ (light blue) $< \tau_1$ (blue). B–H show enlargements, and further enlargements, for seven representative areas in (B): the Adriatic RBA (#6), (C) the Sardinia RBA (#23), (D) the Sicily RBA (#22), (E) the Puglia RBA (#17), (F) the Arno RBA (#9), (G) the Liguria RBA (#5), (F) the Veneto-Venezia-Giulia RBA (#3). E, F, G, H show the same four representative areas in Fig. 2C–F. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

5. Results

5.1. Models' predictive performance

To evaluate the model performance, we confront the median and the

interquartile range of the distributions of the CV metric (Fig. 5a), assuming models with $CV \leq 0.33$ are better than models with $CV \geq 0.50$ – the thresholds represent conditions in which uncertainty is low compared to the central value. We first observe that a reduced spread of the interquartile range characterizes less uncertain models (Fig. 5a).

Fig. 4. Maps show modelled water depth W , in four classes, for the shortest return period τ_3 . See Fig. 2 for the location of the four areas, and Fig. 3 for the corresponding potentially inundated areas (PIAs). See text for explanation (§ 4.8).

RBA #21, 11, 2, 10, 6, 9, 5, 20, and 23, covering 86,929 km² (28.34% of Italy) have $0.20 \leq CV \leq 0.33$, $0.15 \leq TR_\sigma \leq 0.22$, and $0.55 \leq TR_\mu \leq 0.84$, where $TR_\mu = 0.25$ corresponds to a random result for a four-class classification. For these RBAs, the location and extent of the predicted PIAs,

and the corresponding predicted water depth, are reliable predictors of flood hazard and risk zoning, at the scale of the investigation. Except for Veneto RBA (#3), the only RBA where the model performances are poor (Table 1), in the remaining 13 RBAs (191,715 km², 62.51%), the PIA

Fig. 5. Boxplots show the distributions (a) of the CV performance metrics obtained for the 23 RBAs, and (b) of the CV metrics obtained for the 32 combinations of the seven model covariates (L, H, D, V, S, O, G). Colours show number of covariates in each model. The number of data used to construct the boxplots varies with the number of covariate combinations. For models with 2 or 7 covariates, boxplots were built using 32 sets of validation data. For models with 3 or 6 covariates, boxplots were built using 160 sets of validation data. For models with 4 or 5 covariates, boxplots were built using 320 sets of validation data. For geographical location, and main characteristics of each RBA see Fig. 2 and Table 1. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

zonings and the corresponding water depth estimates are useful for a preliminary evaluation of the flood hazard risk zoning, mostly in the large portion of the river network where the FPAs are not present.

Comparison of the extent of the PIAs and FPAs reveals that the PIAs are systematically larger than the FPAs (Fig. 6). This was expected. For a few RBAs (#6, 7, 8, 9, 10) the PIAs do not expand significantly the FPAs. Except for #7, these RBAs have a total FPA larger than 10% of the RBA. For 13 RBAs (#5, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23) covering 156,047 km² (50,88%), the percentage of terrain modelled as potentially inundated (i.e., the PIAs) increases to about 10–35% i.e., a tenfold

increase.

We note that the RBAs with the best performances (#21, 11, 2, 10, 6, 9, 5, 20, 23) are small or medium in size (Fig. 2A, Table 1). This is because in small RBAs the landscape is more homogeneous, facilitating the binary classification, whereas in large RBAs (#1, 3) the landscape is more heterogeneous (encompassing mountains, hills, and large plains), and the classification models perform less effectively (low TR_p) or less homogeneously (high TR_c). Also, in small and medium size RBAs the role of artificial channels, levees, and other flood protection structures not captured by the TinItaly DEM is limited. We conclude that the classification models performed less effectively in large RBAs characterized by significant morphological variability. We further note that the interquartile range is much larger for the models built using 4 or 5 covariates than for those built using less (2, 3) or more (6, 7) covariates (Fig. 5a), whereas it is not much dissimilar for the different covariate combinations (Fig. 5b). We conclude that the larger interquartile range is due to the larger sets of validation data used for 4, 5 covariates models (320 validation sets), and that the uncertainty measured by the interquartile range for the models built with 3 or 6 (160 sets) or 2 or 7 (32 sets) covariates is underestimated (Fig. 5).

5.2. Model covariates

The model performances vary depending on the number and the combination of the covariates (Fig. 5b, Table 1), with the “best” performances obtained for the LH, LHO, LHG, LHGO, LHS, LHSO, LHSG, and LHSGO combinations. For most of the RBAs, the performances of the simplest LH models are comparable to the performances of the most complex models that used more hydro-morphometric covariates. This confirms that the planimetric distance (L) and the elevation difference (H) between a grid cell and the nearest stream are relevant measures to discriminate between PIAs and MAs (Degiorgis et al., 2012; Gnecco et al., 2017; Manfreda et al., 2015; Try et al., 2019).

Further inspection of Table 1 reveals that the best model performances were obtained using combinations of three to five covariates, with most of the best models using combinations of three covariates. The observation confirms that using a model of higher complexity does not result in better models, necessarily. We further note that, in addition to the L and H covariates, the hydro-morphometric variables that most entered the classification models were the stream order O, the local terrain roughness G, and the local terrain slope, S. Only five of the best combinations included the V covariate and none the D covariate. We conclude that, in our study areas, the elevation difference and the hydrological distance to the basin outlet are not (D), or are only poorly (V)

Fig. 6. Scatter plot compares for each RBAs (coloured dots) the percentage of the CV best flood-prone zonings (y-axes), to the FPA zonings (x-axes). Green colours show better zonings, and red colours show poorer zonings, based on the CV index value. Size of dots show areal extent of the RBAs. See text for explanation (§ 5.3). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

relevant to discriminate between PIAs and MAs.

5.3. Potentially inundated areas and flood water depth

Fig. 3 portrays a map showing the PIAs for the three considered return periods. Overall, of the total extent of the PIAs (90,804 km²), 8.29% (−1.44%) were mapped considering the τ_1 return period, 13.27% (+1.19%) the τ_2 period, and 78.44% (+0.25%) the τ_3 period. Comparison of the PIAs with the FPAs (Fig. 2) reveals that the total extent of the PIAs is systematically larger than the extent of the FPAs (Fig. 6). At the national scale, the differences between the area extent of the PIAs and the FPAs are −28.5% (τ_1), −3.5% (τ_2), and 479.3% (τ_3), with a total increment of 157.2%.

Ultimately, we compared the water depth map obtained applying the Flood-SHE procedure for the whole of Italy to a similar map prepared for Europe by Alfieri et al. (2014, 2015) at a 100 m × 100 m ground resolution, and for three return periods (20, 100, and 200 yr). In Italy, the continental map identifies as potentially inundated 4.46% of the territory for the 20-yr return periods, 5.15% for the 100-yr return period, and 5.36% for the 200-year return period. The corresponding maps prepared in this work cover 23.23% (τ_3), 27.16% (τ_2), and 29.61% (τ_1) of the territory. The differences reveal a severe underestimation of the European map, justified by the coarse resolution of the synoptic map that considered only large rivers (Alfieri et al., 2014, 2015).

Considering only grid cells common to both maps, the continental map has a median (99th percentile) water depth of 1.21 m (7.62 m), 1.41 m (8.69 m), and 1.48 m (9.03 m), in the inundation areas computed for the 20, 100, and 200-yr return periods. The corresponding figures from this work (Fig. 4) are 0.67 m (τ_3), 1.33 m (τ_2), and 1.55 m (τ_1), with the 99th percentile always larger than 4.00 m. We note that the mean and the median of the differences between the European and the Italian maps are close to 0.0 – at least for τ_2 and τ_1 – and negative, and that the interquartile range of the differences is nearly symmetrical around the median. We take these as evidences of the similarity of the two maps.

6. Flood hazard zonings and risk mitigation

6.1. Flood hazard zonings and the human consequences of floods

Flood casualties are a measure of flood risk to the population (IPCC, 2014; Tanoue et al., 2016). If the original FPAs or the modelled PIAs are to be used to determine flood risk, they should include most of the sites where flood events with harmful human consequences have occurred. For Italy, a catalogue of flood events with deaths, missing persons, injured people, homeless and evacuees, was compiled by Guzzetti et al. (2005) and updated by Salvati et al. (2010, 2018). We confront the portion of the catalogue from 1920 to 2019 with the extent of the FPAs (Fig. 2B) and the PIAs (Fig. 3A), limiting the analysis to the 206 point sites for which the geographical location is considered accurate (Salvati et al., 2010). To account for uncertainty in the geographical location of the sites of harmful floods, we added a 100 m buffer around each point. We found that of the 206 sites, 135 (65.5%) were inside the FPAs, and 194 (94.2%) were inside the PIAs. This is an increase of 28.6%, which measures the better ability of the PIAs to determine where flood risk to the population exists in Italy. We consider this a significant improvement of the PIA compared to the FPA zonings.

We note that in all the RBAs, the PIAs contain the same (#9, 8, 13, 20, 4, 10, 11) or a larger number of harmful flood sites than the FPAs, including twelve RBAs (#2, 3, 12, 15, 16, 17, 18, 14, 20, 21, 22, 23) where the increase in the number of sites of harmful floods exceeds 30%. We conclude that the improvement of the PIA over the FPA zonings in capturing flood risk to the population is common throughout Italy. We further note that of the 206 sites of harmful floods, nine (4.4%) were located outside both the FPAs and the PIAs, in five RBAs (#1, 12, 17, 6, 22).

6.2. Quality analysis of the flood hazard zonings

To quantify the quality of the FPA and PIA zonings, we use four indices – IT, IH, IK, IR – that measure independent hydrological, topographical, and flood risk characteristics related to the quality of a flood hazard zoning designed for flood risk assessment, with emphasis on risk to the population.

IT compares the topology of the synthetic river network in an FPA or PIA against the network topology in the entire RBA, and it is the ratio between the maximum topological distance (Claps et al., 1996) in the FPA or PIA, and in the corresponding RBA. For the FPAs, we obtained $0.38 (\#3) \leq IT \leq 1.0 (\#8, 13, 20, 23, 11)$, whereas for the PIAs, $IT = 1.0$ for all RBAs.

IH compares the distribution of terrain elevation in an FPA or PIA zoning against terrain elevation in the entire RBA, and it is the ratio between the hypsometric integral (Strahler, 1952) in the FPA or PIA, and in the corresponding RBA. For the FPAs, we obtained $0.002 (\#4) \leq IH \leq 0.11 (\#11)$, whereas for the PIAs, $0.26 (\#2) \leq IH \leq 0.29 (\#16)$.

IK compares the distribution of terrain elevation along the river network in an FPA or PIA zoning against the elevation along the river network in the entire RBA, and it corresponds to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov “d” statistic (Davis, 1986), which measures the maximum vertical distance between the empirical cumulative distribution functions (ECDF) of terrain elevation along the river network in an FPA or PIA, and in the entire RBA. Large values of IK are obtained for very different river elevation distributions in the FPAs or PIAs and the RBAs. For the FPAs, $0.077 (\#11) \leq IK \leq 0.6 (\#2)$, whereas for the PIAs, $2.4 \times 10^{-4} (\#11) \leq IK \leq 0.022 (\#15)$.

Ultimately, IR compares flood risk to the population in an FPA or PIA, and in the entire RBA, and it is the ratio between the number of flood casualties, homeless, and evacuees in an FPA or PIA, and in the entire RBA. For the FPAs, we found $0.0 (\#16, 2) \leq IR \leq 1.0 (\#9, 8, 13, 4, 10, 11)$, whereas for the PIAs, we found $0.67 (\#17) \leq IR \leq 1.0$ (in 17 of the 23 RBAs).

Fig. 7 compares the four (normalized) indices computed for the FPAs and PIAs in the 23 RBAs. Visual inspection of the charts reveals the variability of the indices. For the FPAs, we first note that nine RBAs (39.14%) have $IR \geq 0.75$, seven (30.43%) $0.5 \leq IR < 0.75$, and seven (30.43%) $IR < 0.5$, indicating that in only nine RBAs (#9, 8, 7, 19, 5, 13, 4, 10, 11) the FPAs contain 75% or more of the known flood human consequences in the period 1920–2019, and in seven RBAs (#2, 3, 12, 15, 16, 17, 22) the FPAs contain 50% or less of the known flood human consequences in the period. The figures are far from optimal for a land zoning aimed at reducing the human consequences of river inundations. Instead, if one considers the PIAs, 22 RBAs (95.6%) have $IR \geq 0.75$, and one RBA (4.4%) has $0.5 \leq IR < 0.75$, indicating that most of the PIAs contain 75% or more of the total number of known flood human consequences in the period 1920–2019. We conclude that the PIAs are better zonings to reduce the human consequences of river inundations in Italy.

We note that in all the PIAs, $IT = 1.00$, whereas in the FPAs, $0.38 \leq IT \leq 1.00$ ($\mu = 0.89$, $\sigma = 0.16$), with only seven RBAs (#1, 9, 8, 13, 20, 23, 11) having $IT = 1.00$. We further note that, in the PIAs, $0.0002 \leq IK \leq 0.0222$ ($\mu = 0.0059$, $\sigma = 0.0057$), whereas in the FPAs, $0.0766 \leq IK \leq 0.6001$ ($\mu = 0.3194$, $\sigma = 0.1327$). Ultimately, we note that the IH indices computed for the PIAs and the FPAs are both low (Fig. 7). However, for four RBAs (#16, 23, 13, 17) the IH values for the PIAs are significantly larger than the corresponding values for the FPAs. Overall, we conclude that the PIAs zonings capture the river network topology and the river elevation profiles significantly better than the FPAs, and we consider them potentially better terrain subdivisions to evaluate flood risk to the population in the RBAs.

In Fig. 7, the (normalized) areas shown by the coloured diamonds measure the quality of the FPA or PIA zonings for each RBAs, with larger (smaller) diamonds reflecting higher (lower) quality zonings. The shape of the diamonds reveals the contribution of the four indices to the

Fig. 7. Polar charts compare the quality indices I_T , I_H , I_K , and I_R , computed for the FPAs and PIAs in the 23 RBAs. I_T , I_H , and I_R rescaled to a common range [0–1], with 0 assigned to the less performing values, and 1 to best performing values. I_K index first transformed taking the minimum values equal to 0 and the maximum values equal to 1, and then taking $I_K = 1 - I_K$. Diamond area measures quality of the zonings, with larger (smaller) diamonds reflecting higher (lower) quality.

overall quality of the flood zonings. Taking QFPA and QPIA to measure the area of the FPA and PIA diamonds – and, hence, as estimates of the quality of the corresponding flood zonings – we note that $1.04 \leq QPIA \leq 2.00$ ($\mu = 1.38$, $\sigma = 0.27$) and $0.0019 \leq QFPA \leq 1.29$ ($\mu = 0.49$, $\sigma = 0.36$). Fig. 8 compares the quality scores for the FPA and the PIA flood hazard zonings in the 23 RBAs. We observe that the quality scores for the PIAs are systematically larger than the scores for the FPAs, with a slightly reduced quality range, and a linear trend relating the quality scores. This confirms that the PIA zonings are potentially better terrain subdivisions than the FPA zonings to evaluate flood risk in the RBAs.

7. Discussion

Our exercise of applying the data-driven Flood-SHE procedure for the delineation of “potentially inundated areas” (PIAs, Fig. 3) in the 23

RBAs in Italy, and their comparison with the corresponding “flood prone areas (FPAs, Fig. 2) defined through consolidated hydro-dynamic flood routing and inundation modelling, allows for several considerations.

For our data-driven approach we used a logit model (Cox, 1958; Venable and Ripley, 2002; Tolles and Meurer, 2016), one of several data-driven classification techniques used in the literature for the delineation of areas that can be inundated by river floods (Manfreda et al., 2014, 2015; Shafizadeh-Moghadam et al., 2018; Siahkamari et al., 2018; Arabameri et al., 2019; Choubin et al., 2019; Costache, 2019; Davoudi Moghaddam et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019; Mind’je et al., 2019). This is a simple, binary classification model, but Flood-SHE is independent of the classification approach, and more complex approaches can be used, including e.g., neural networks, machine learning, and deep learning approaches (Degiorgis et al., 2012; Khosravi et al., 2016; Samela et al., 2017; Tehrany et al., 2017; Abiodun et al., 2018;

Fig. 8. Scatter plot shows for each RBA the quality score for the FPAs (x-axis) and the PIA (y-axis) flood hazard zonings. Size of dots show areal extent of the RBAs. See text for explanation (§ 6.2).

Pouyanfar et al., 2018; Carleo et al., 2019; Davoudi Moghaddam et al., 2019; Manfreda and Samela, 2019). However, given the reduced set of model covariates, and the uncertainties inherent in the terrain and the FPAs data, adoption of more advanced classification approaches was not justified. Advanced classification approaches may be beneficial in the case of a “multi-model” approach, where various classification models are trained using different approaches, and the results are combined to obtain “optimal” PIA zonations and their related uncertainties.

In the literature, works that have used data-driven approaches exploited geographical inundation data obtained from different sources, including (i) “event inundation maps” showing areas inundated by a single flood, or maps showing multiple floods in a period (Smith, 1997; Khosravi et al., 2016; Rosser et al., 2017; Ahmadlou et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019; Shen et al., 2019), and (ii) areas outlined by a single or by multiple, hydro-dynamic flood routing and inundation models as potentially inundated, for single or for multiple return periods (Hunter et al., 2007; Tingsanchali and Karim, 2010; Degiorgis et al., 2012; Manfreda et al., 2014, 2015, 2015; Demir and Kisi, 2016; Golshan et al., 2016; Rahmati et al., 2016b; Teng et al., 2017). A limitation of these works was the limited availability of “inundated points”, typically less than 200 points (Choubin et al., 2019; Kanani-Sadat et al., 2019; Siahkamari et al., 2018). In addition, points identified in non-flood-prone areas, essential for the classification, were selected using subjective (Khosravi et al., 2016; Chapi et al., 2017; Costache, 2019; Wang et al., 2019a) or poorly defined (Tehrany et al., 2015b, 2019a; Wang et al., 2015; Rahmati et al., 2016a; Shafizadeh-Moghadam et al., 2018; Choubin et al., 2019; Davoudi Moghaddam et al., 2019; Mind’je et al., 2019) criteria that are difficult – or impossible – to reproduce (Khosravi et al., 2016; Chapi et al., 2017; Costache, 2019; Wang et al., 2019a). The Flood-SHE procedure overcomes these limitations by adopting a rigorous approach that exploits existing FPA zonings and a clear – and optimal – definition of the marginal areas (MAs).

The quality of the modelled PIAs depends on the quality and accuracy of both the FPAs and MAs. In principle, if the information on the

“flood prone” and the “non-flood-prone” areas, was accurate and representative of an entire RBA, differences between the FPA and the PIA zonings were expected only where the FPAs had not been identified. Reality is different. The quality of the FPA zonings varies unevenly within each RBA, and across the RBAs. Except for RBAs #8, 9, 10, and 11, in Tuscany, Central Italy, and for parts of the Po River basin (#1) in Northern Italy, most of the FPAs do not cover the whole extent of an RBA with the same accuracy, and are limited to the main trunks of the river networks, and to the areas where vulnerable elements are most abundant. This is matched by the large number of harmful human consequences found in the FPAs, which include more than 50% of the total number of historical flood human consequences in a relatively limited areal extent. Conversely, close examination of the PIAs reveals that the potentially inundated areas are typically distributed around the entire river network instead of being limited to the main trunks of the network, or in areas where vulnerable elements are particularly abundant.

For most of the RBAs, the increment in the extent of the PIAs compared to the corresponding FPAs is, on average, about 400%, with a maximum of 1600% (# 4) (Table 1, Fig. 6). However, in the RBAs where the quality index QFPA is large (#9, 10, 11, in Tuscany) or medium (#8, 7, 1, 6), the increment is in the range from 15% to 90% ($\mu = 34.7\%$). We conclude that the PIAs expand significantly the flood-prone areas identified by the FPAs only where the FPAs zonings are not sufficiently accurate or detailed. We note (Table 1) that in the RBA #9, 10, 11, in Tuscany, the FPA flood hazard zoning is the result of a mixed approach that exploited accurate physically-based modelling, geomorphological inference, and historical data (Autorità di Bacino Distrettuale dell’Appennino Settentrionale, 2016). This explains why the data-driven Flood-SHE procedure that exploits morphometric and hydrological covariates has resulted in a flood zoning which is very similar to the FPA zoning. We further note that QFPA values are typically lower than the corresponding QPIA, and have a larger variability (Fig. 8). We conclude that, at the scale of the investigation, the Flood-SHE procedure resulted in more homogeneous flood hazard and risk zonings than the original (heterogeneous) FPAs. This is relevant, considering that in Italy national and regional scale flood vulnerability and risk assessments (Trigila et al., 2015; Roder et al., 2017) suffer from the heterogeneity of the FPA zonings.

We note that the quality of a PIA delineated exploiting the Flood-SHE procedure depends on the quality, density, and representativeness of the river network, contingent on the quality, resolution, and representativeness of the DEM. Where a river network does not exist (e.g., in a karst landscape, in a glacial landscape) or cannot be extracted from the DEM (e.g., because of a too coarse resolution or the DEM), the Flood-SHE procedure cannot delineate the PIAs, or cannot delineate the PIAs accurately. Where the river network extracted from the DEM is dense – because i.e., the DEM is representative of a true high-density drainage network, or the minimum size of the contributing area used to extract the network is small – Flood-SHE tends to delineate a larger number of larger PIAs than in the areas where the river network is sparse. In our work, we used the 10 m \times 10 m TinItaly DEM, and we preferred dense digital river networks. In flat terrain, typically in large alluvial plains, this has resulted in the identification of PIAs even in areas not drained by major rivers (Fig. 3E). Albeit these areas may not be inundated by river floods, they can be covered occasionally by water due to high intensity rainfall events, because of the lack of surface drainage. Where the DEM does not capture the geometry of natural or artificial levees, drainages, or other flood protection structures, Flood-SHE cannot delineate the PIAs accurately. Typically, in these areas, Flood-SHE has delineated PIAs larger than one would have expected, and larger than the corresponding FPAs determined typically using better resolution and higher quality DEMs. Overall, in these areas, Flood-SHE results in more conservative delineations of the areas that can be potentially inundated by floods than the FPA zonings. In many of these areas, and particularly where large alluvial plains are protected by natural or artificial levees, or where rivers flow above the thalweg, the PIAs capture the potential

consequences of levee breaching (Ashley and Ashley, 2008; Flor et al., 2010; Bayoumi and Meguid, 2011; Orlandini et al., 2015; Salvati et al., 2018). We maintain that this is an important information for a comprehensive flood hazard assessment, and for long-term risk mitigation efforts.

In our work, we attempted to determine the depth of the river flood inundation in the PIAs. We acknowledge that the approach is unsophisticated and can result in local errors, particularly in areas characterized by large or very large alluvial plains where the vertical accuracy of the TinItaly DEM may not be adequate for accurate, local estimations of the water depth. Further, the TinItaly DEM is a digital representation of the topographic surface based on a triangulated irregular network. In flat terrain, this may result in locally unrealistic “flat triangles” and in related locally unrealistic estimates of the flood water depth. Despite these clear (local) limitations, comparison of the flood water depth maps obtained by Flood-SHE with the similar map prepared by Alfieri et al. (2014) for Europe shows that the two estimates are similar, but the PIAs maps cover a much larger area than the synoptic maps prepared for Europe.

For our PIA zonings we did not use information on the velocity of the water flow. We acknowledge that this is a limitation, as water velocity is important for estimating flood risk to the population (Milanesi et al., 2015; Arrighi et al., 2017). But, accurate information on water velocity is difficult to obtain for large areas, and reliable velocity modelling is feasible only where accurate high-resolution terrain models are available (Costabile et al., 2020; Papaioannu et al., 2016), which are also difficult to obtain for large areas. Moreover, in our study area flood fatalities have occurred also where flow velocity was low, or negligible (Salvati et al., 2018), suggesting that information of water flow is not mandatory for flood hazard or risk mapping, as also dictated by the European Flood Risk Management Directive (Van Alphen et al., 2009). We further note that quantitative, spatially-distributed estimations of flood risk to population can be obtained without considering flow velocity (Guzzetti et al., 2005; Salvati et al., 2012).

We stress that the data-driven PIA zonings produced by the Flood-SHE procedure complement, and do not replace, the FPAs flood hazard zonings prepared through hydrodynamic flood routing and inundation modelling. The PIAs zonings can prove particularly valuable in areas and along portions of the river networks for which FPAs zonings are not available. They may also prove useful to identify and rank portions of an RBA, and sections of a river network, that require additional or improved FPA flood zonings.

Ultimately, we tested the Flood-SHE procedure in a variety of landscape and environmental settings, using FPA zonings prepared by different hydro-dynamic flood routing and inundation modelling approaches (Table 1) using terrain and hydrological information of different accuracy and quality. Based on the results obtained, we maintain that the Flood-SHE procedure is general, and applicable in a variety of settings for which adequate terrain information and information on flood prone areas is available.

8. Conclusions

Exploiting information on the extent of “flood prone areas” (FPAs) defined through hydrodynamic flood routing and inundation modelling, and using hydro-morphometric variables obtained from the 10 m × 10 m TinItaly DEM (Tarquini et al., 2007), the data-driven, Flood-SHE procedure was able to delineate “potentially inundated areas” (PIAs) in the 23 river basin authorities (RBAs) covering the Italian land territory (Fig. 2). Analysis of the results obtained allow for the following conclusions.

Where sufficient information on FPAs is available, together with a sufficiently detailed digital representation of the terrain, data-driven modelling approaches – like Flood-SHE – can delineate accurately over large areas PIAs that match closely the corresponding inundation areas defined by physically-based hydrological modelling approaches

(Grimaldi et al., 2013; Manfreda et al., 2015; Rahmati et al., 2016b; Bermúdez et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019b). An advantage of the data-driven zonings is that they can be prepared for areas not covered by the physically-based models. The quality of the data-driven models will depend on the quality of the original hydrological zonations, on the accuracy of the terrain information, and on the significance of the statistical classification.

Our experiment confirmed that a reduced number of hydro-morphometric variables is sufficient to construct reliable models and PIA zonings, most of which were superior to models constructed using a larger number of variables. This confirms that using a model of higher complexity does not result in a better model, necessarily, and opens to the possibility of using the Flood-SHE procedure in other areas where sufficient information is available.

In the literature, most of the data-driven attempts at delineating PIAs have been based on limited information on flooded sites at point locations. Use of millions of data points obtained from existing FPA zonings has improved the statistical classification, and the corresponding inundation hazard zonings.

In the 23 RBAs in Italy, our data-driven approach has outlined larger to much larger areas as potentially subject of being inundated (Figs. 3 and 6), compared to the corresponding flood zonings prepared by the hydro-dynamic models (Fig. 2). This depends primarily on the fact that the data-driven PIA zonings were constructed to cover most of the river network, whereas the hydrological FPA zonings were conducted in specific sections of the river network, or in areas of particular interest. Our quality analysis revealed that the PIAs expanded significantly the FPAs zonings only where the FPAs zonings were not accurate or detailed.

Comparison of the data-driven PIA and the FPA zonings revealed that the PIAs capture more effectively the location of the sites with historical flood human consequences between 1920 and 2019. We conclude that the PIAs are better geographical representations of the areas subject to flood risk to the population in Italy.

We expect the PIAs zonings prepared in this work to complement the pre-existing FPA zonings where they are available, and to expand the FPA zonings where they are not available, jointly contributing as non-structural (“soft”) measures to the mitigation of flood risk in Italy.

Credit author statement

Ivan Marchesini: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Software, Resources, Formal analysis, Data Curation, Validation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization. **Paola Salvati:** Validation, Data Curation, Visualization, Project administration, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing. **Mauro Rossi:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Writing - Review & Editing. **Marco Donnini:** Validation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization. **Simone Sterlacchini:** Validation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Fausto Guzzetti:** Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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improving the article substantially.

Appendix. List of variables

Variables used in the text

Variable	Description
d	Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic
CV	Coefficient of variation
D	Planimetric distance between each grid cell and the basin outlet, measured along the hydrologic flow direction (m)
G	Local terrain roughness (Grohmann et al., 2011)
H	Elevation difference between each grid cell and the nearest stream, measured along the hydrologic flow direction (m)
E	Number of hexagons containing grid cells classified as FPAs or MAs
IH	Quality index based on hypsometric integral
IK	Quality index based on river elevation profile
IR	Quality index based on flood risk to the population
IT	Quality index based on river network topology
L	Planimetric distance between each grid cell and the nearest stream, measured along the hydrologic flow direction (m)
O	Order of the stream channel into which each grid cell drains Shreve (1966)
QFPA	Quality index for FPA based on IT, IH, IK, and IR
QPIA	Quality index for PIA based on IT, IH, IK, and IR
S	Local terrain slope (degree)
TR _σ	Standard deviation of the True Rate
TR _μ	Average of the True Rate
T	Flow accumulation threshold
V	Elevation difference between each grid cell and the basin outlet, measured along the hydrologic flow direction (m)
W	Flood water depth (m)
μ	Mean
σ	Standard deviation
τ	Return period (year)

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